

The Influence of the Snowball Throwing Learning Model on Social Studies Learning Outcomes for Class VIII Students of UPTD SMP Negeri 1 Pematang Siantar

Jeli Lusiana DT Padang^{1*}, Binsar Tison Gultom², Pdt. Paulina HN Sirait³
Universitas HKBP Nommensen Pematang Siantar, Indonesia

Corresponding Author: Jeli Lusiana DT Padang; jelipadang@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

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This type of research is quasi-experimental research with a quantitative approach. The population of this study was all class VIII students at UPTD SMP Negeri 1 Pematang Siantar, totaling 347 students. The sample in this study consisted of two classes, namely: Class VIII⁴ as a control class with a total of 32 students and Class VIII⁷ as an experimental class with a total of 32 students. In this research the instrument used was the test. The data collection technique uses tests, observation and documentation. Meanwhile, the data analysis techniques used are normality test, homogeneity test and t hypothesis testing (*Independent Samples Test*) using the SPSS version 23 application. Based on the results of data analysis using t hypothesis testing (*Independent Samples Test*), it was obtained that $t = 2,504$ and t_{table} (at the 5% significance level) = 1,999, meaning $t_{count} > t_{table}$. In accordance with the criteria, H_0 is accepted if $t_{count} < t_{table}$ and H_0 is rejected if $t_{count} > t_{table}$. So, it can be concluded that there is an influence of the *Snowball Throwing Learning Model* on the Social Sciences Learning Outcomes of Class VIII UPTD Students at SMP Negeri 1 Pematang Siantar.

INTRODUCTION

Teaching effectiveness in a good learning interaction process is all the efforts made by the teacher to help students learn well. In improving the quality of education, teachers are people who have an important role because they are the ones who transfer knowledge to their students. Teachers continue to develop various special models so that the material presented can reap maximum results. There are various kinds of learning models that teachers can apply in the teaching and learning process.

A learning model is a plan or pattern that is used as a guide in planning learning activities in the classroom. Learning models are very important to use in the teaching and learning process. This learning model is used to increase student motivation in following existing learning so that it will influence student learning outcomes. However, it cannot be denied that the use of learning models that are not optimal can also be a problem in the world of education.

Learning outcomes are learning achievements achieved by students through teaching and learning activities. Learning outcomes have a very important role in the learning process, because with learning outcomes a teacher can receive information regarding students' progress in achieving their learning goals through the process of subsequent teaching and learning activities.

Based on the results of observations made by researchers as students who had carried out Field Experience Practices (PPL) in 2022 at UPTD SMP Negeri 1 Pematang Siantar, the researcher obtained information through interviews conducted with one of the class VIII social studies teachers at UPTD SMP Negeri 1 Pematang Siantar, One of the problems faced is that teachers are not optimal in implementing existing learning models, while the learning model that teachers always use every time they teach is the conventional learning model in the form of lectures and questions and answers.

From these observations it was found that students' scores in social studies subjects were still low, as evidenced by the fact that there were still students who did not reach the Minimum Completeness Criteria (KKM) in one of the learning evaluation test results conducted by the teacher. The KKM that must be achieved by class VIII students in the social studies subject is 70. In class VIII-4, 15 students completed it and 17 students did not complete it. In class VIII-7 there were 13 students who completed and 19 students who did not complete. From these data it can be concluded that social studies learning at the school is less than optimal, resulting in students' grades in social

studies subjects being still low. One of the reasons is the lack of optimal use of the learning models used by teachers when teaching.

One learning model that can be used to attract students' attention is to use the *Snowball Throwing type of cooperative learning model*. The *Snowball Throwing* learning strategy or what is also often known as *Snowball Fight* is a learning strategy that was first adopted from a physical game where a lump of snow was thrown with the intention of hitting another person.

Therefore, through the use of the *Snowball Throwing* learning model, students in class VIII UPTD SMP Negeri 1 Pematang Siantar are expected to be able to improve student learning outcomes for the better so that they can achieve the predetermined KKM, namely 70. This can enable the school to be able to develop innovative lessons, creative, so that it can improve student learning outcomes and student competence in the academic field.

Guided by the explanation above, the author would like to conduct research with the title " The Influence of The Snowball Throwing Learning Model on The Science Learning Outcomes of Class VIII Students of UPTD SMP Negeri 1 Pematang Siantar".

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

1. Learner Model

The learning model is a form of learning that is depicted from beginning to end carried out by the teacher. Learning models can also be said to be tricks or supports that teachers use during the learning process to assist the teacher in conveying teaching material to students. A learning model is a frame for implementing certain learning approaches, methods, strategies and techniques (Helmiati 2016:19). The learning model is the entire series of presentation of teaching material which includes all aspects before, during and after learning carried out by the teacher, as well as all related facilities which are used directly or indirectly in the teaching and learning process (Istarani 2015:1).

2. Snowball Throwing

Snowball Throwing learning model consists of a series of delivery of teaching materials, starting with delivering the material, then forming groups and their respective group leaders. After that, the group leaders returned to their respective groups to explain what the teacher had conveyed to their students. Huda (2017:226), the *snowball throwing* learning model is a learning model that was first adopted from a

physical game where a lump of snow was thrown with the intention of hitting another person. Musdalipa (2022:21), the *Snowball Throwing* learning model is a learning model that uses paper balls containing questions.

3. Learning outcomes

Sappalle (2022:11), said that learning outcomes are a process for determining students' learning values through assessment activities or measuring learning outcomes. Sudjana (in Prasetya 2012: 107), believes that learning outcomes are the abilities that students have after the students receive their learning experience. Meanwhile, Afandi (2013:6) said that learning outcomes are a process of change in intellectual abilities (cognitive), interest or emotional abilities (affective) and fine and gross motor skills (psychomotor) in students. He said that learning outcomes are the abilities that students have. after following a teaching and learning process and producing changes in the student for the better, both cognitive, affective and psychomotor changes.

METHODS

The type of research carried out is descriptive quantitative research. This research is descriptive research because it aims to describe the facts and characteristics of a particular population or area systematically, factually and thoroughly. According to Sugiyono (2017:11) that "Quantitative Research can be interpreted as A research method based on positivist philosophy, used to research certain populations or samples, data collection using research instruments, quantitative/statistical data analysis, with the aim of testing the hypothesis that has been applied.

Based on the researcher's title "The Influence of the Snowball Throwing Learning Model on Social Studies Learning Outcomes for Class VIII Students of UPTD SMP NEGERI 1 PEMATANG SIANTAR. This research was carried out at SMPN 1 Pematang Siantar for 2 weeks from 2 October 2023 to 14 October 2023. The population in this study were all students in class VIII of SMPN 1 Pematang Siantar in 11 classes totaling 347 students . The sample in this research was classes VIII-4 and VIII-7 with a total of 64 students.

RESULTS

Research Instrument Trial Results

Instrument Validity Test

The validity test in this research used SPSS version 23 and Ms. Excel 2007. The level used to test the validity of the instrument is 0.05%. Based on the results of the validity test tested on class IX1 UPTD SMP Negeri 1 Pematang Siantar with a total of 31 students and a total of 25 questions.

Items that are declared valid are items that have a correlation value (r) > 0.354 , while items that have a correlation value (r) > 0.354 are valid questionnaire items. This can be concluded that for the questions it is known that there are 20 items that have a correlation value (r) > 0.354 and as many as 5 questions (r) < 0.354 , it is known that 20 questions have valid data and 5 are invalid. Therefore, the 5 invalid questions were not used for further research

Instrument Reliability Test

For the questionnaire reliability criteria, if $r_{count} > r_{table}$ with a significant level ($\alpha = 0.05$) then the questionnaire is said to be reliable. However, if $r_{count} \leq r_{table}$ then the questionnaire is considered to have no reliability. If the *Cronbach Alpha value* is > 0.60 it is said to be reliable, but if the *Cronbach Alpha value* is < 0.60 it is said to be unreliable.

From the data obtained, it is known that *the Cronbach Alpha* obtained was $0.742 > 0.60$. From the results of calculating the reliability of the snowball throwing learning model, it can be concluded that the research instrument used is reliable.

Question Difficulty Level

In testing the difficulty level of questions, researchers used SPSS version 23, which was done by comparing the mean value on the SPSS output with the question difficulty level index, namely: 0.00 - 0.30 (Difficult), 0.31 - 0.70 (Medium), 0.71 - 1.00 (Easy). Based on the test of the difficulty level of the questions carried out with the help of SPSS version 23, it can be seen that from the 20 questions there are 8 questions in the easy category, 10 questions in the medium category and 2 questions in the difficult category.

The Power of Different Questions

The item discrimination test in this study was used to determine the ability of the items to differentiate between students with high ability and students with low ability. The following are the different power criteria.

Based on the test of differentiating power of questions carried out with the help of SPSS version 23, it can be seen that from the 20 questions there are 7 questions in the good category and 13 questions in the fair category.

Data analysis technique

Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Table 1
Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Pre-test Experiment	32	55	15	70	47.81	14,421
Post-Test Experiment	32	40	55	95	78.91	10,529
Control Pre-Test	32	45	40	85	62.34	11,070
Control Post-Test	32	50	40	90	71.41	13,273
Valid N (listwise)	32					

Based on the table above, the minimum score obtained in the experimental *pretest* is 15 and the maximum score is 70. Meanwhile in the control class, the minimum score obtained in the *pre-test* is 40 and the maximum score is 85.

After being given conventional learning treatment in the form of a lecture in the control class and the *snowball throwing learning model treatment* in the experimental class, a re-test was carried out for students in the form of a *post test*. The minimum score obtained in the experimental *post-test* was 55 and the maximum score was 95, while the minimum *post-test score* obtained in the control class was 40 and the maximum score was 90. Therefore it can be concluded that there is a difference in scores between the control class and the experiment. Tests carried out in the experimental class using the *snowball throwing learning model* had higher scores than in the control class which used the lecture learning model.

Test Data Analysis Techniques

Data Normality Test

Table 2
Normality Test Results

Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistics	Df	Sig.	Statistics	Df	Sig.
Pre-test Experiment	.128	32	,195	,958	32	,235
Post-test Experiment	.137	32	.136	,941	32	,078
Pre-test Control	,130	32	,180	,971	32	,521
Control Post-test	,145	32	,084	,932	32	,044

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the significance value in the *Kolmogorov Smirnov column* is >0.05 , so it can be concluded that the four data are normally distributed.

Homogeneity test

Table 3
Pre-Test Homogeneity Test
Test of Homogeneity of Variance

		Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Hasil Belajar	Based on Mean	2.142	1	62	.148
	Based on Median	1.862	1	62	.177
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	1.862	1	58.742	.178
	Based on trimmed mean	2.075	1	62	.155

Based on the results of the average score variant homogeneity test or *Based on Mean In the pretest* of students in the experimental class and control class, a significant value of 0.148 was obtained. Based on the decision criteria , if the resulting

significance value is > 0.05 , then the data can be said to be homogeneous . So it can be concluded that the *post-test scores* for each group are the same (homogeneous).

Table 4.12
Post-Test Homogeneity Test
Test of Homogeneity of Variance

		Levene Statistics	df1	df2	Sig.
Learning outcomes	Based on Mean	.952	1	62	.333
	Based on Median	.902	1	62	.346
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	.902	1	58.250	.346
	Based on trimmed mean	1.134	1	62	.291

Based on the results of the average score variant homogeneity test or *Based on Mean posttest* for students in the experimental class and control class, a significant value of 0.333 was obtained. Based on the decision criteria , if the resulting significance value is > 0.05 , then the data can be said to be homogeneous . So it can be concluded that the *post scores* for each group are the same (homogeneous).

Hypothesis testing

Table 4.13
Hypothesis Test Results
Independent Samples Test

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
F	Sig.	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
							Lower	Upper

Hasil Belajar	Equal variance assumed	.952	.333	2.504	62	.015	7.500	2.995	1.513	13.487
	Equal variance not assumed			2.504	58.947	.015	7.500	2.995	1.507	13.493

Based on the table above, the degree of freedom for this research is 62, with a significance value of 0.05, so the significance of the $t_{table\ value}$ is 1.999. Meanwhile, the calculated t_{value} obtained is 2.504, if compared with $t_{calculated} > t_{table}$, it can be concluded that H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected, which means that there is an influence of *the snowball throwing learning model* on student learning outcomes.

DISCUSSION

The research was conducted to determine the influence of the Snowball Throwing Learning Model on the Social Sciences Learning Outcomes of Class VIII Students at SMP Negeri 1 Pematang Siantar.

This research was conducted at UPTD SMP Negeri 1 Pematang Siantar. This research aims to determine the influence of the *Snowball Throwing Learning Model* on the Social Sciences Learning Outcomes of Class VIII UPTD Students at SMP Negeri 1 Pematang Siantar. The material taught in this research is social mobility material. The sample used consisted of 2 classes, namely the control class and the experimental class. The class used for the control class is class VIII⁴ and the experimental class is class VIII⁷.

In the control class the learning model used during the teaching process is the conventional model in the form of lectures and questions and answers, while in the experimental class the learning model used is the *snowball throwing learning model*. Before being given the learning model treatment, students were first given an initial test in the form of a *pre-test*, but previously these questions had been tried out on class IX¹ students, the *pre-test* given to the sample consisted of 20 multiple choice questions, after being given the *pre-test*, so given learning model treatment, conventional learning model for the control class and *snowball throwing learning model* for the experimental

class. After being given the learning model treatment, the next step is to give students a final test in the form of a *post-test* of 20 multiple choice questions.

After getting the students' social studies learning results, the scores are then tested using a normality test to see whether the questions are normally distributed or not. Based on the normality test, the data obtained from the social studies learning results of the control and experimental classes were normally distributed. Then the next test used is the homogeneity test, and the significant value obtained in the homogeneity test is > 0.05 , which means that the questions are homogeneous or the same. And the last test used was hypothesis testing with t testing (*Independent samples test*), the value obtained was, $t_{\text{count}} 2,504 > t_{\text{table}} 1,999$, which means there is an influence of the *snowball throwing learning model* on student learning outcomes.

This research is also in line with research previously conducted by Sriwahyuni Endang, with the research title *The Influence of the Snowball Throwing Learning Model on Learning Outcomes in Class VIII Social Sciences Learning at YPI 3 Way Jepara Islamic Middle School*. In her research, Sriwahyuni Endang concluded that there was an influence of the *snowball throwing learning model* on student learning outcomes, this is proven by the $t_{\text{calculated}}$ value obtained at 8.486 and the t_{table} value at 1.734 with a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$ or the $t_{\text{calculated}}$ value $> t_{\text{table}}$, then H_0 is rejected. So it can be said that there is an influence of the *snowball throwing learning model* on learning outcomes.

Based on the research results obtained and support from previous studies conducted by other researchers, it can be concluded that the *snowball throwing learning model* can improve students' social studies learning outcomes.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of research and hypothesis testing carried out by researchers, it can be concluded that: There is an influence of the *snowball throwing learning model* on students' social studies learning outcomes, this is proven by the $t_{\text{calculated}}$ value obtained at 2,504, and the t_{table} value at 1,999 when compared to $t_{\text{calculated}} > t_{\text{table}}$, it can be concluded that h_a is accepted and h_0 is rejected, which means that there is an influence of the *snowball throwing learning model* on student learning outcomes.

FURTHER STUDY

Based on the conclusions above, the suggestions that researchers can give are as follows:

1. *The snowball throwing learning model* , which can involve students to be more active when learning and reduce students' level of boredom in learning.
2. For students, by using the *snowball throwing learning model* , it is hoped that they will be more active when studying.

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